

HOME & ABROAD

2022 - 2023

THE LANGUAGE ISSUE

EDITORS IN CHIEF

PARKER KENEE - MEDICAL SCHOOL CLASS OF 2024

KOSHMA ESWARMOORTHY - MEDICAL SCHOOL CLASS OF 2026

SENIOR ADVISORS

PARKER DAVIS - MEDICAL SCHOOL CLASS OF 2025

ADDITIONAL EDITING PROVIDED BY

DR. MARY CHANG

DR. ANGELA MIHALIC

CREATIVE DIRECTOR/GRAPHIC DESIGNER

NASHRA JAVED - MEDICAL SCHOOL CLASS OF 2024

STAFF WRITERS

HEBA ZAKARIA - MEDICAL SCHOOL CLASS OF 2025

BENJAMIN POPOKH - MEDICAL SCHOOL CLASS OF 2026

AISHWARYA IYER - MEDICAL SCHOOL CLASS OF 2023

JENNIFER FOSTER - MEDICAL SCHOOL CLASS OF 2024

ISAAC MYRES - MEDICAL SCHOOL CLASS OF 2024

PARKER DAVIS - MEDICAL SCHOOL CLASS OF 2025

PARKER KENEE - MEDICAL SCHOOL CLASS OF 2024

HISTORY AND VISION

Home & Abroad was founded in 2014 by two second-year medical students: Aloysus Lawong & Jie Yao. Upon matriculating, Aloysus observed that countless, commendable global health ventures were being undertaken by students and faculty alike at UTSW. Armed with the conviction that these burgeoning global health enthusiasts make up the fabric of a growing and interdependent health community at “Home” and “Abroad,” together they went to work. With the endorsement and support of colleagues and the backing of the Office of Global Health and UTSW leadership, Home & Abroad was born. Our mission is to provide a varied perspective on global and national health endeavors and highlight initiative and achievements by the student body, faculty and friends. Our vision is to become the premier literary forum on campus, utilizing multidisciplinary approaches to address challenges in global and national medicine by providing our readers insightful and accurate information on pertinent global health topics.

CONTACT US

For letters to the editor, submissions, and reprints, please email homeandabroadmag@gmail.com

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Dear Reader,

We hope this letter finds you well. It is with great pleasure that we welcome you to the latest edition of Home and Abroad. This issue is dedicated to the critical and evolving field of global health in the context of language. Our team has worked tirelessly to curate a diverse and informative collection of articles and features that we believe will captivate your interest and deepen your understanding of language within the scope of the global health landscape.

The pursuit of global health is an ever-evolving journey, shaped by the dynamic interplay of science, politics, culture, and the countless individuals and organizations committed to the well-being of people worldwide. In this issue, we delve into a myriad of topics that reflect the multifaceted nature of global health and how language affects our approach to global health. Language as we know it is very differently approached based on our individual experiences and our exposure to the human condition. From thought-provoking essays on socio-economic disparities to exploring ways humanity has crossed language boundaries, this issue features pieces that delve into the ethical and social dilemmas that global health practitioners often face.

We would like to express our gratitude to you, our readers, contributors, and the entire Home and Abroad team, for your unwavering support. Together, we are fostering a community of informed individuals who care deeply about the health and well-being of people around the world.

Please enjoy this issue of Home and Abroad, and feel free to reach out to us with your feedback. We are committed to improving with each issue and providing a platform for all things related to global health.

Thank you for being part of this journey, and for your support throughout it all.

Sincerely,

Parker Kenée
Editor-in-Chief

Koshma Eswaramoorthy
Editor-in-Chief

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LOST IN KINDERGARTEN

FOUND IN EMPATHY

The white, popcorn-textured wall stood before me, a canvas for my racing thoughts. The laughter and sounds of children playing faded away as I stood alone, wondering why I couldn't join them. In a corner of the kindergarten classroom, I felt isolated and misunderstood. But this experience, this moment of confusion, taught me to see the world through a different lens. This marked the beginning of my ongoing journey to empathize with those who face language barriers.

By Heba Zakaria

Born in the U.S., I had just moved back from living in Jordan, where I had attended pre-K. My parents had made sure that I had a strong foundation in Arabic, my mother tongue, before introducing me to English. But on my first day of kindergarten in the suburbs of Arlington, TX, I felt lost and out of place.

Time out. These two words capture the essence of my first year in school. Kindergarten is a difficult milestone for many children, but for me, it felt impossible. As I watched the other kids around me make friends, I faced the daunting challenge of being understood, not just by my peers, but by my teacher too. I tried to communicate in the only way I knew how: by speaking Arabic. Unfortunately, instead of helping me, my teacher punished me for it. I was sent to the corner of the classroom after asking to use the restroom. My teacher's unexpected response was based on a misunderstanding; she believed I was cursing when, in fact, I was simply trying to communicate my needs. This experience had a significant impact on my confidence and ability to connect with others, and it highlights the importance of cultural awareness and acceptance in the classroom and beyond.

Despite harboring resentment towards my teacher's actions, the experience has bestowed upon me a heightened sense of empathy towards individuals, particularly patients, who are faced with a language barrier. I remember feeling invisible and unimportant, like a forgotten character

in a story. I can only fathom the similar emotional turbulence that a patient in the healthcare system may undergo during a time when they need help the most. Non-English speaking patients face greater challenges in accessing primary care, leading to suboptimal experiences and increased vulnerability to health problems [1]. This is a glaring issue that deserves our attention and efforts to ensure everyone can access quality preventative and acute healthcare.

During my clinical rotations as a medical student, I've observed some of the challenges faced by both healthcare professionals and non-English speaking patients. An article in the *British Journal of General Practice* highlights that language interpreting services in primary care are being underutilized despite their crucial role as the first point of contact for patients [2]. Utilizing language interpretation services for non-English speaking patients necessitates a significantly greater amount of time compared to their English-speaking counterparts. In large hospitals and health systems, the high patient volume makes it impractical to rely on in-person interpreters. Consequently, phone-based interpretation services are commonly used, but they can be hindered by occasional connectivity issues, which may lead to less accurate interpretations or require patients and healthcare professionals to repeat themselves. This not only lengthens the duration of the visit but also elevates the risk of medical errors, making the use of interpreters burdensome and unreliable at times. The impact of these

language barriers extends beyond the mere exchange of information that aids healthcare professionals in diagnosing and offering suitable treatment to patients. It obstructs patients' capacity to experience being heard, comforted, and reassured. Consequently, it hampers our ability to empathize and fulfill our roles as healers when we cannot fully comprehend how our patients feel.

Although spoken English is often the foremost consideration when contemplating language barriers in the United States, it's important to recognize that even fluent English speakers can encounter language barriers in healthcare due to the use of medical jargon by healthcare professionals. The mastery of technical terminology is a result of years of medical education and practice, which can make it difficult to convey critical information to patients, even those that are English proficient. Moreover, other marginalized groups in the healthcare system, such as individuals who are D/deaf, blind, or

deafblind, faced significant challenges navigating the healthcare system, and these shortcomings were underscored by the added layer of difficulty imposed by PPE* during the COVID-19 pandemic [2].

Enhancing our cultural awareness, understanding of language interpretation services, and driving change at the policy, practice, and educational levels has been widely proposed as a solution to address disparities in healthcare [1]. My initial struggle with language barriers in kindergarten set me on a path of empathy and awareness, especially in the context of healthcare. The experiences of non-English speaking patients facing linguistic obstacles and the challenges healthcare professionals encounter in providing proper care highlight the pressing need for bridging these gaps.

*PPE: Personal protective equipment

2

A SILENT CONVERSATION IN GLOBAL HEALTH

“Hello, my name Benji. Nice meet you.” I said. Not in those exact words, but instead by shifting my hands in a choreographed movement, a dance-like introduction. I was speaking American Sign Language, a tongue unique in that it requires minimal use of the actual tongue. American Sign Language, or ASL, is one of roughly 300 sign languages used across the globe [1]. As evidenced by the way I phrased my introduction, ASL is not simply a direct translation of the spoken English language into signs. In fact, ASL is most closely related to French Sign Language (LSF), established by Dr. Thomas Gallaudet and born of a mixture between local unofficial signs and LSF [2]. Thus, individuals from England and America may both speak the English language, but their signed languages are entirely unique from one another.

Historically, members of the Deaf and Hard of Hearing community have been marginalized as a disabled group. In fact, as recently as the 19th and 20th centuries, deaf children would have their hands bound to tables in order to force them to attempt oral speech [3]. Just a century ago in the U.S., there was a strong emphasis on preventing deaf people from intermarrying and reproducing [4]. Today, members of these communities seek recognition as a language minority, rather than a disability group. A common suggestion for bridging communication gaps between hearing and hard of hearing individuals is direct text-to-text dialogue. While this may be effective in many cases, deaf people often have difficulty interpreting spoken languages, even in their written form. Upon completion of high school, deaf people have a “median reading level... comparable to that of 8-year old hearing children” [5]. Considering that they

are learning the meaning of characters that they haven’t learned to pronounce or heard spoken, this deficit makes sense. As a result, communication via signed language is imperative in effective dialogue between the hearing and non-hearing population.

This language barrier has tangible impacts on healthcare. Deaf patients tend to seek primary care less often, though they are more likely to visit the emergency department than their hearing peers. In a poll taken of deaf individuals, 16.2% reported visiting the ER at least twice in the past year, while a National Health Interview Survey of hearing individuals found only 6.9% of US adults visited the ER twice or more [6]. How can we improve access to healthcare for deaf individuals, not only in the U.S., but globally? A team from the Netherlands explored this question during the COVID-19 pandemic, discussing healthcare challenges with patients using Sign Language of the Netherlands (NGT). Concerns immediately apparent during the pandemic were restrictions on interpreters entering hospitals, poor quality of video translation services, and face masks inhibiting the potential for lip reading. The research team decided to collect phrases most commonly used in diagnosing COVID-19, and they generated 139 high quality video translations. In addition, they developed a virtual avatar translation format with 7,720 sentences, as well as a user interface that allowed patients to navigate between the human and avatar translations. The team found that while the avatar system was easy to update and broaden, it did not convey body language as naturally as patients would have liked. Doctors were able to use the system to ask patients questions, however, there

were some limitations present. If a doctor used the system to ask an open-ended question, the elaborate answer from the deaf patient would be incomprehensible to the physician. The system was far better for yes/no questions, where a doctor could display a closed-ended question through the virtual avatar, and the patient could simply nod yes or shake their head no. While this approach may seem clunky and challenging to navigate, it is a fundamental step towards improving healthcare of deaf individuals [5].

When practicing healthcare globally, there is always a challenge of communication between practitioners and the population they are serving. In addition to a frank language barrier, there are usually significant socioeconomic and cultural differences between the practitioner and patient. The assistance of locals can occasionally ameliorate this via translation services. However, finding translators for the signed language of a foreign country can prove to be an even greater challenge. For example, a 2008 sociolinguistic survey of the Honduran deaf community [7] found that there were only “five to eight certified [Honduran Sign Language] interpreters” in the entire country. Meanwhile, there are an estimated 70,000 deaf individuals living in Honduras.

In an ideal world, there would be time to learn both the spoken and signed languages of the countries we visit. Unfortunately, this is unrealistic for the busy physician. Learning just a few conversational phrases in a given sign language,

however, has the potential to relieve stress for deaf patients. Other small steps include offering printed images and medical brochures at the appropriate reading level. On a broader scale, expanding signed language interpretation technology would be useful both worldwide and domestically. Working with developers and native speakers to optimize signed healthcare translation is something physicians can do today. Because sign language relies heavily on the unique layout of each conversation, the primary challenge is to generate AI that can quickly update based on conversational context. This still requires a human element of language synthesis, and it is imperative for physicians to recognize this unique linguistic element.

Taking on these challenges at an individual and systemic level may appear daunting to the already overworked healthcare practitioner, but small steps each day can lead to better health outcomes worldwide. As with any patient population, patience, empathy, and understanding are key. The Hard of Hearing population is one that can especially benefit from a simple smile, gentle hand, and warm presence. Through individual advocacy and improvements in signed language interpretation technology, I am confident that we can make significant strides in overcoming this communication barrier across the globe.

By Benjamin Popokh

3

THE LANGUAGE OF LIFESTYLE MODIFICATION

BY AISHWARYA IYER

When it comes to treating and preventing the most common chronic diseases in the U.S.—coronary artery disease, hypertension, diabetes—lifestyle modification is repeatedly shown to be as, if not more, effective than treatment with medications [1-6]. However, making lifestyle modifications can be quite challenging. Though evidence shows that small steps can add up to make a significant difference [7,8], change is hard. Importantly, when it comes to counseling patients on changing aspects of their daily lifestyle, the specificity of our recommendations matters. The language we use in counseling patients on lifestyle modifications needs a serious overhaul; it's not enough to tell someone to "make time for exercise" or "eat healthier." What do those statements actually mean? How can someone implement these recommendations, when change is so very challenging? Here are some tips to help you be a more effective agent of change, next time you're faced with the challenge of counseling your patient on lifestyle modifications:

BE SPECIFIC.

Specificity is everything. Too often, we make broad statements like “make healthier choices” which, owing to their vagueness, are hard to translate into action. Although the official recommendation may state “get 150 minutes of exercise in a week,” it’s important to partner with your patient to translate that broad recommendation into small, specific, and actionable steps that they can feasibly follow. This will be guided by the

patient’s daily routine and what they feel they have time for. An example might be: breaking down “150 minutes of exercise a week” from “30 minutes of exercise a day” to 10, 5, or 2-minute bite-size pieces scattered throughout the day. If going for a 20-minute walk feels too daunting, suggest taking the stairs as an alternative to the elevator (if they are able-bodied). If making time for a 10-minute yoga session feels impossible to your patient, ask them if they can take a 2 minute stretch break during lunch (if they work a job that offers them one), or 30 seconds to do some chair yoga (if they work a desk job).

SPECIFICITY MATTERS—

The more granular you are in the ideas you offer, the more helpful it’ll be and the easier you’ll find it to partner with your patients to help brainstorm ways that they can make those small, actionable changes in their lifestyle.

PERSONALIZE YOUR RECOMMENDATIONS TO THE PATIENT IN FRONT OF YOU.

Any discussion around lifestyle modifications would be remiss if it did not acknowledge the broader factors—those structural determinants of health—that influence a person’s ability to achieve those lifestyle modifications. Even in the examples noted above, factors such as disability and the type of job your patient works can dramatically influence the relevance or utility of the recommendations you make. Being thoughtful about the context within which our patients live is crucially important to making appropriate recommendations. Understanding what is or is not feasible for them will change the way that we counsel. For example, telling a patient who lives in an unsafe neighborhood, or one with poorly maintained roads and sidewalks, to walk outside for 30 minutes a day misses the mark. Instead, find ways to feasibly achieve the same goal within the reality of their circumstances—a number of workouts can be done in the safety and privacy of one’s own home, whether it’s a guided video on YouTube, walking indoors, or even marching in place for the same amount of time. Such recommendations should be tailored to the patient based on the particular factors at play in their life, such as prior level of activity, motivation, physical, mental, and emotional barriers, and reliable Internet access.

DON’T FORGET THEIR CULTURAL CONTEXT.

Remember to make recommendations in the context of the individual person in front of you, considering facets of their identity that may influence the effectiveness (or even sometimes, relevance) of the recommendations you’re looking to make. For instance, people who come from cultures where the foods we eat at home are different than the ones our traditional American or Western counterparts eat, don’t find utility in apps like MyFitnessPal that help you track your dietary intake, because the things we eat are literally not on the app and very difficult (sometimes impossible!) to add in manually. Apps such as MyFitnessPal are not always inclusive and perpetuate a restrictive, Eurocentric view of health and nutrition that does not reflect the true extent of healthy eating patterns out there. Similarly, recommending the Mediterranean diet because it currently has the most evidence to support positive health outcomes [9] can fall short because it fails to recognize that cultures around the world, particularly in South, East, and Southeast Asia, have existed for generations on diets that look very different but show similarly positive “results.” Therefore, we must consider that perhaps our current understanding of nutrition is limited because this Western, Eurocentric bias exists in the evidence base [10]. Ideally, a shift in this will come as we work to diversify our research and uplift perspectives beyond those that center whiteness—in the meantime, when caring for patients who come from non-Western cultures, we must first work to understand what they eat on a regular basis, and make dietary recommendations within that context, finding small ways to make positive change that align with their cultural values [11].

CHECK YOUR IMPLICIT BIASES.

We live in a society that moralizes health and personal responsibility and creates a narrative that weight loss is purely a matter of willpower or choice, rather than recognizing that many factors beyond individual control—including genetics, availability of green spaces and fresh food, and other structural, “upstream” determinants [12]—play into a person’s ability to manage their weight. This overwhelming narrative, indoctrinated into us by society and reinforced by the lack of thoughtful, informed education around weight management in medical training, adds to the shame and stigma fat people in particular experience too often in health care. We know that fatphobic language is shaming, stigmatizing, and turns patients off from seeking health care entirely [13-15]. What can we do to address this? An easy first step is to recognize that BMI (the Body Mass Index) is a flawed and outdated measure designed by a mathematician that is not informative of a patient’s true state of health[16,17], and that substituting this with other methods of evaluation such as body fat percentage, hip-to-waist ratio can give us a better sense of assessing patients

who may be at higher risk for health complications such as metabolic syndrome. When it comes to encouraging lifestyle modifications for treatment or prevention of chronic conditions such as hypertension, diabetes, or obesity (defined by many major medical associations as “a complex, chronic, relapsing, progressive condition that is associated with, but not dependent on, lifestyle”) [18], work to adopt a weight-inclusive approach to lifestyle counseling [19]. Ask for the patient’s permission to discuss their weight, and use neutral language focused on the quality of health measures (e.g., sleep, stress relief) rather than language hyper-focused on weight loss as the ultimate determinant of successful lifestyle change. When it comes to counseling on dietary changes, be cognizant of how recommendations like tracking calorie intake using apps like MyFitnessPal can be very triggering for patients with a history of an eating disorder and encourages even people without a formally diagnosed eating disorder to engage in disordered eating habits. Successful dietary modification is more than just “calories in vs. calories out”—framing it in this way is not only not backed by evidence, but can cause more harm than good [20].

Ultimately, many of the things on this list boil down to adopting an approach that is thoughtful, intentional, and individually designed. It can be easy for us to make recommendations that don't land well with our patients if we draw only from our own lived experience, rather than theirs. Always working to be intentional about checking our own implicit biases, which are informed by our experiences and the ways in which we see and experience the world, can go a long way in combating this pitfall, helping us better meet our patients where they are, and helping them achieve better health.

4

THE CLASS OF BABEL

By Jennifer Foster

I began volunteering at women's shelters when I was 19 with the sole intention of teaching them yoga. I believed deeply in the healing power of yoga and meditation, and wanted to share the profound peace I found with just about everyone I met. There was a blissful naivete in how easy I thought it would be: I would teach them yoga, and then we would all be healed. There was a problem, and I could provide the solution. I had a profound connection to women's issues from a young age. As a high school student, I watched many of my friends suffer through abusive relationships that were often written off as "young love" or simply toxic. Our education had not prepared us for this: as young Protestant women, we were told to be abstinent, to sign a pledge to God, to obey "or else." We didn't know what to do when our boyfriends tracked our locations, screamed at us for minor transgressions, or, in some cases, hit us. Although 10% of high school girls in Texas report having been in an abusive relationship, our health education refused to acknowledge this fact. Our school officials, parents, and spiritual leaders tiptoed around the big, mean elephant in the room for the sake of their comfort, disregarding our wellbeing. This perturbed me deeply. When Mosaic, a transitional housing center for women surviving domestic violence and human trafficking, accepted my request to teach yoga at their shelter, I was elated. My purpose was realized! I was naively unaware of the journey ahead. It was never, ever going to be that easy.

I remember the first cold November evening I taught at the shelter. I sat, covered in yoga blankets, shivering in front of the stained-glass windows. The building was an old monastery that housed monks when the property still belonged to the church. Remnants of its previous life lingered on: sharp lead paneling, as well as windows adorned with deep purple and yellow flowers. The ceilings were tall and ornately carved. Thick drafts of cold air blew through the wide double doors to the back of the building where we sat. This holy

room was renovated into a children's play room and, now, a makeshift yoga studio.

I studied the women in front of me and could tell I had a motley crew: women of all ages, walks of life, and cultures sat before me. The gravity of the moment was not lost on me. We had journeyed from our different corners of the world and walked our life paths at our own paces simply to meet there in that moment, in that room. It was, frankly, divine. I took a deep breath and introduced myself to the women who sat circled around me.

I was met with blank expressions.

"No English," stated one brave woman in the front room.

"Oh, excuse me?" I responded. I was maybe six months into my yoga teaching career and was sweating profusely just sitting in front of a group of people. No English? I could barely teach yoga in English. How was I supposed to teach it in another language?

She shook her head in response. The other women turned to each other mumbling, curious as to what was happening. I heard the woman who originally spoke up, Luisa, turn to her friend and speak a few sentences in Spanish. I watched the other women turn to each other and speak in languages I did not fully recognize. One pair was speaking in Mandarin—I recognized a couple phrases from a two week study abroad trip I did the previous year. The rest of the group was a complete toss-up. They had all connected with someone sharing their language. I was the odd one out

I burst into a fit of nervous laughter and the other women in the room laughed along, though confused as to what was so funny. On one

hand, I was mortified. Here I was trying to fulfill what I believed to be my calling, and I couldn't even communicate with these women. I also felt embarrassingly uncultured. Why couldn't I learn to speak a language sooner? I had tried and failed many times. At first, in high school, I took French, then in college I took Spanish. Most recently, I even sat in a beginner Mandarin course. Ultimately, I knew that the reason I had never succeeded previously was that I was too embarrassed to practice speaking a different language, especially to a native speaker. I could barely speak English at times, my childhood speech impediment breaking through at the most inopportune moments. Other times, I could hear the Southern twang I was raised on, running wild in rural East Texas. My mother has a deep drawl that would sneak its way into my "yes ma'ams" and "thank yous." Still, I could hear my grandmother's Swedish accent. My mother sometimes broke into it when she was frustrated with one of her many children. One time, in middle school, a boy kept poking my back with his sharpened pencil, which was, in retrospect, a failed attempt at flirting. In the heat of the moment, I whipped my head around and, in a perfect Swedish accent and cadence, berated him. I never heard the end of it from my classmates. Words would become tangled in my mouth. A knot formed of undecipherable gibberish. I would throw the knot away and never try again.

As I soon discovered, no one in the make-shift yoga studio spoke more than a few words of English. I stumbled through class and tumbled over my words, which I now realize ultimately didn't matter as no one could understand a word of what I was saying. I did my best to demonstrate

each and every pose but left defeated and red in the face. The women I taught, however, were profusely gracious. I heard many different variations of “thank you.” My ego refused to accept them.

While ruminating on my own struggles with language, I began to understand the strength of the women I was surrounded by. Speaking another language is painstakingly vulnerable. These women had been uprooted from their home countries and forcibly taken to a land where they had to learn a different language. They could not leave the monastery and escape their insecurity, as I could. Growing up in the South, I knew how unkind people could be to those who do not speak English fluently. American culture is riddled with cheap jokes about mispronunciations of English phrases. People here did not take kindly to outsiders, even if those outsiders were brought here against their will. I thought of Brené Brown describing vulnerability as an “arena” that we gear up to enter when we try new things or open ourselves up to criticism [1]. My privilege was in my ability to walk out of the arena. For these women, they entered the arena every day whether they wanted to or not. If they could do it, I reasoned, why couldn't I?

I cannot pinpoint the exact moment in which teaching a class full of women who could not understand my words no longer felt like a monumental task. In my memory, our understanding and trust of one another grew slowly but steadily. I would demonstrate a pose, and they would copy me to the best of their ability. I would exaggerate movements to correct them and they picked up quickly, faster than I expected. Although they could not understand my elaborate cues or well-prepared speeches, they returned week after

week. I learned their names and they learned mine. I soon discovered that I could not speak with my hands, as the women would copy my particular hand movements, unaware that it was not a part of the pose. Many times we broke into fits of laughter upon realizing our miscommunication. The system we created was quite simple. I taught them yoga. They taught me how to love without ever having to share the same words. Our language was the feeling in the room when we were together, the light shining through stained-glass, soft giggles during weird yoga poses, the beating of our hearts, and the movement of our breath. Our language was our presence. Our language was our connection.

These women went on to graduate the program, and a new group with several English speakers joined. While my friends moved on to start the next chapter of their lives, the lesson that class taught me lingers. I could be brave, too. Though I still feel that nervous pit in my stomach when attempting to speak Spanish with patients at the hospital or saying goodbye in a different language, I have learned to ignore it. I have found an endless source of inspiration for entering the arena, even when I don't technically need to, especially when it feels uncomfortable. The attempt to communicate in a second language is a radical act of vulnerability and its reward is connection. I feel it now with those women, though I fear I will never see them again. Their memory remains a powerful reminder to be fearless in my never-ending search for meaning through connection.

Where Words Don't Belong

By Isaac Myres

AS A WRITER, I believe in words. I believe in the power that words have to change the very landscape of human thought and emotion, and action. I believe that words can connect, intertwine and weave a narrative from the worlds-apart perspectives of you and me. I believe that words have the power to free the human soul from the chains of misunderstanding and isolation; then we can ascend to heights of understanding and expression that soar above confusion.

AS A DOCTOR, I believe in words. I believe words can carry more than their assigned meanings as my patient searches for something to represent their thoughts and feelings.

I BELIEVE THAT WORDS ARE AMONG OUR GREATEST TOOLS TO HEAL, TO CURE, TO COMFORT, AND TO CARE.

AS A HUMAN, I believe in words. I believe words, when chosen deliberately, are akin to the divine in their power, their magnitude, their majesty, their effect.

HOWEVER.

It was 11am and we were beginning our third case of the day. I was a brand new medical student, watching from the corner and over shoulders in fascination and awe at the unfolding world of otolaryngology before me.

Words were exchanged efficiently and rapidly there in the operating room. Sizes, tools, maneuvers, instructions, requests, jokes, questions, and answers were all floated around the room as we worked. Between cases, the air would settle as I sat reflecting on a stool in the corner.

Soon, the next patient would be brought in, and the words again began to swirl around. My eyes locked on the little four-year-old girl sitting up on the bed that was comically oversized for her. Her little blonde pigtails stuck up on both sides of her head and her arms were wrapped around a teddy bear that was half of her size. I could see her eyes scanning the room in

fear, looking up at the lights and scopes and machines beeping around her. As her bed came to a stop in the middle of the room, our eyes met.

Maybe it was her eyes searching for anything familiar or comforting aside from the teddy bear she clung to. Maybe it was the reminder of my two nieces, her same age. Maybe it was the tracheostomy tube in her neck and the novelty of the laryngoplasty I was about to see. Whatever it was, as she and I made eye contact, something struck a chord.

The desire to comfort her grew within me as I watched those panicked eyes darting around the room. All I wanted to do was help her feel at ease. I wanted her to know that all these people moving around cared about her and her safety. I wanted her to know that the cacophony of whirring machines would eventually give her back the ability to breathe and to speak to her loved ones in the waiting room.

The doctors typed words into their computers, the rest of the staff talked as they prepared the room, and yet the little girl said nothing. No words came to mind that I thought could calm her from my little stool in the corner, but we continued to stare at each other.

Finally, I waved. Soon, with hesitation, she raised her hand and waved back. Both of us were nervous and new here, both of us comforting each other as we waved. I began to wiggle my fingers. She laughed and tried as hard as she could to bend each finger in her best attempt to wiggle back. I laughed too at her earnest attempt and in that moment, without a word, we were both calmed.

In a flash, the anesthesiologist put the mask on her face and began counting down from ten. People were still moving about and the machines kept on humming, but I remained on my corner stool, thinking about what had happened.

As a writer, a doctor, a human...I believe there is a time and place for words.

BUT THERE IS ALSO A TIME AND A PLACE WHERE WORDS DON'T BELONG.

6

A COMPASSIONATE TOMORROW

By Parker Davis

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted healthcare inequality like no other event in recent memory. The shortcomings of many developed nations in ensuring equitable resource sharing exacerbated already tenuous relations and helped fan the flames of intense racism and dangerous nationalism. Disastrously, our sense of empathy was the first of many crucial safety nets to fail. People were quick to turn on one another, citing differences in political and cultural ideology as the basis for failing to contain the deadly virus. These divisions, both within the United States and elsewhere, created a fragmented and ineffective response to the outbreak. Cycles of intense finger-pointing and social shaming threatened to unravel any attempt at cohesion in the midst of the disease.

Taking meaningful steps toward the resolution of the pandemic required immense patience as public health officials tried to get the whole country moving in the same direction. The social disunity created by the virus caused widespread resistance to containment and prevention efforts; disbelief in science and a general mistrust of healthcare led many individuals to reject these measures. Many more, however, did not have the luxury of choice: the option to participate in crucial public health movements—like screening and vaccination—was simply never

presented to them. Amid the chaos of the pandemic, healthcare seemingly turned a blind eye toward those of lower socioeconomic status, as well as racial and ethnic minorities. Consequently, these populations experienced a greater disease burden than others. The people in need of the most help received less than their fair share.

HOW COULD THIS HAPPEN?

In a culture that, at least on the surface, appears more aware than ever before of disparities among its constituents, it seems unthinkable that we could have let so egregious an effacement of those morals go unnoticed. Perhaps a fear of the unknown in COVID overrode our sense of empathy. Perhaps, when push turned to shove, the things we proclaimed to hold in the highest regard—equality and justice for all—turned out to be irrelevant. Whether consciously or not, the chasms in healthcare utilization between racial and economic classes widened drastically, irrevocably, the opposite edges receding farther and farther away.

At least part of the issue resides in how information from the CDC and NIH was conveyed to the masses. In many cases, blanket statements and mandates about how to address the spread of the virus and protect oneself were applicable only for the

middle and upper classes—those with the means to purchase disinfecting supplies, masks, and other PPE in large quantities, for example. For some groups, what should be done and what could be done were two circles of a Venn Diagram with very little overlap. The intense demand for PPE meant that often individuals had to choose between items like masks and their next meal. All of this resulted, predictably, in higher rates of healthcare utilization in traditionally underserved populations.

No matter the cause, the inequity of the pandemic healthcare response served to reinforce many boundaries that traditionally disenfranchised groups already faced. It is thus the responsibility of those in positions of power to begin tearing down these barriers. If the period from 2020 until the present was defined by reactionary measures from a global society caught off guard, then the

next period in our public health saga must be defined by a righting of the wrongs caused by such a reaction. The success of this crusade will depend in large part on our compassion for those on the short end of the proverbial stick. But it is one thing to claim empathy, and another to practice it. Living compassionately, not simply being compassionate, requires making a conscious effort to identify and address disparities between oneself and another. It requires seeing beyond the sociopolitical mirage to find the shared humanity of us all. At its very best, a compassionate life can bring justice to many hundreds or thousands in need. A cultural movement toward overwhelming and unconditional empathy has the potential to stamp out inequality in any form it takes.

LANGUAGE: THE TRENDS OF 2022

*GRAPHS AND DATA ADAPTED FROM INFORMATION PUBLISHED BY DUOLINGO BLOG [1]

BY PARKER KENEE

In 2023, information – data – is more ubiquitous and accessible than ever. “How many minutes did I spend staring at my phone today?” “How long would it take me to bike to Sacramento?” “What is the conversion rate of the US dollar to Japanese Yen?” The answer to any of these questions is seconds away. Information pertaining to language is no exception. The best place to start, perhaps, is the application “Duolingo”. With over 100 courses in 40+ languages, and completely free to use, it should come as no surprise that Duolingo has become exceedingly popular...to the tune of over 500 MILLION users from around the world! [1] With so many active users, Duolingo provides a wealth of knowledge about the recent trends in language acquisition and solidification. Here are some of the highlights from their annually published report:

1. The Most Popular Languages remain Stable

More dramatic proportional changes are often observed in less-popular languages, but the top three remained stable from 2021 to 2022: English (1st or 2nd in 130 and 131 countries, respectively), Spanish (90 and 81 countries), and French (90 and 96 countries). The continued strength of these “big three” is often attributed to practical and professional motivators. The top 10 languages across the world, in order: English, Spanish, French, German, Japanese, Italian, Korean, Chinese, Russian, and Hindi [1].

2. Ukraine: The World Wants to Help

Following the invasion of Ukraine by Russia in February 2022, the number of worldwide users learning Ukrainian increased by over 1.3 million near instantaneously [1]. This number continued to climb through March and remained at similar levels throughout the remainder of 2022 and the ongoing Ukraine-Russia conflict. Countries receiving the highest number of refugees from Ukraine saw some of the highest proportional increases in Ukrainian language learners: 1651% in Germany, 1615% in Poland, and 1515% in Czechia. The observed movements in Ukrainian refugees were also reflected in the ways Ukrainians themselves interacted with Duolingo: In Germany, German

rose to the second most popular language course – likely a reflection of the learning interests of incoming Ukrainians.

Duolingo also lent its support to the effort, as many Ukrainians sat for the Duolingo English Test (DET) to demonstrate sufficiency in English language for eligibility to learn in international universities. The number of Ukrainians taking the DET increased by 4000% in 2022 from 2021. DET partnered with the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) and Ukraine Global Scholars to provide test fee waivers and support for prospective students seeking refuge from the conflict [1].

3. We're Not Quite Back to Our Traveling Ways

If Duolingo is any indication, “travel” as a language learning motivation remains lower than pre-pandemic levels, and perhaps more surprisingly, lower in 2022 than 2021 [1]. Duolingo collects information about the primary motivation for users to learn various languages. Duolingo also provides commentary about the trend among users in learning a new language to aid them in their exploration of a new place. As the travel industry projects a 2023 increase in domestic and international

travel to near pre-pandemic levels, we may observe more stark increases in “travel” as the cited motivation for learning a language across the board this time next year. Furthermore, a 2022 survey sponsored by Duolingo found that 55% of Latin Americans reported an increased likelihood to travel internationally in 2023, as well as 40% of Indians, 28% of US citizens, and 20% of Germans.

BUT THIS MAY CHANGE IN 2023!

4. We Can Multitask! Maybe?

Can we truly multitask? Who knows. But no one tries more than those living in Finland and the U.K. – the two countries with the most Duolingo users attempting to learn at least three languages simultaneously! Other top five countries include Australia, Estonia, and Brunei. That Finland is on top of the rankings in this category became more intuitive when I learned that 93% of Finnish people are reportedly bi- or multi-lingual. It is also speculated that the U.K.'s high placement in this category is due to the high number of international students traveling there for extended study; it remains the most popular destination for Chinese and Indian students [1].

The saying “Data Is Beautiful” is certainly true, and perhaps even more so when it represents a concerted worldwide effort to support a suffering community, a curiosity to more intimately understand an unfamiliar culture, or the aspiration to explore a foreign land in its most authentic form. Many thanks are owed to Duolingo for highlighting our humanity through data, and for their continued contributions towards connecting our world through the wonders of language. If you have any interest in learning how to unlock the ability to communicate with a new, uniquely experienced community, or even just tapping into underutilized neural territory of your brain, I highly recommend joining the over 500 million users on Duolingo’s free language-learning app!

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parker.kenee@utsouthwestern.edu

koshma.eswarmoorthy@utsouthwestern.edu

